

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF NURSES' ATTITUDES AND SELF-EFFICACY ON
PALLIATIVE CARE DELIVERY IN PAKISTANZareen Yaqoob^{*1}, Shaheena Sardar², Rubina Jabeen³, Zunair Amir⁴^{*1}Post RN 2nd year superior university nursing department Lahore²Post RN Superior University Department of Nursing Lahore³Principal, Superior University Nursing Campus Lahore.⁴Nursing department, superior University, Lahore¹zareenharoon322@gmail.com, ²shaheenasardar160@gamil.com, ³rubinajabeen302@yahoom.com,⁴zunairamir@gmail.comDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16792048>**Keywords**

Palliative care, knowledge, attitude, self-efficacy, nurses, pediatric hospital, Pakistan

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Abstract**Background:** Palliative care is a holistic approach that addresses the physical, emotional, social, and spiritual needs of patients with life-threatening illnesses. In Pakistan, nurses play a central role in palliative care delivery; however, their knowledge, attitude, and self-efficacy significantly influence the quality of care. Limited training and systemic barriers often affect their preparedness and confidence.**Aim:** This study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitude, and self-efficacy of nurses toward palliative care and to examine the relationships among these variables in a pediatric hospital setting in Pakistan.**Methods:** A cross-sectional correlational study was conducted among 171 female nurses working in the Children's Hospital, Lahore. Data were collected using standardized tools: the Palliative Care Quiz for Nursing (PCQN), the Neonatal Palliative Care Attitude Scale (NIPCAS), and the General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE). Descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and regression analysis were performed using SPSS version 23.**Results:** The findings revealed moderate knowledge ($M = 31.19$, $SD = 6.84$), moderate self-efficacy ($M = 18.03$, $SD = 4.46$), and a generally positive attitude ($M = 54.69$, $SD = 13.19$) among participants. Significant positive correlations were found between knowledge, attitude, and self-efficacy ($p < .001$). Gender emerged as a significant predictor of attitude ($\beta = .26$, $p < .01$).**Conclusion:** The study concluded that enhancing nurses' knowledge and self-efficacy is essential for fostering positive attitudes toward palliative care. Structured training programs and supportive clinical environments are recommended to improve palliative care practices**INTRODUCTION**

Palliative care is defined by the World Health Organization as an approach that improves the quality of life of patients and their families facing

problems associated with life-threatening illnesses through prevention and relief of suffering by means of early identification, assessment, and treatment of

pain and other physical, psychosocial, and spiritual issues (World Health Organization, 2020). Self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their capability to organize and execute actions required to manage prospective situations effectively (Bandura, 1997). Attitude is a psychological construct encompassing beliefs, feelings, and behavioral tendencies toward a specific object, person, or concept, which in healthcare influences how care is delivered (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993). In the context of palliative care, nurses' attitudes and self-efficacy directly impact their delivery of quality care to patients facing life-limiting conditions (Kassa et al., 2014).

Globally, an estimated 40 million people annually require palliative care, yet only about 14% receive it (World Health Organization, 2020). Approximately 78% of these individuals live in low- and middle-income countries where palliative care services are limited (Connor & Bermedo, 2020). In Pakistan, palliative care is still developing, and most services are centered in tertiary hospitals, often inaccessible to rural populations (Nishtar et al., 2021). Chronic diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular disease, and end-stage organ failure represent the largest groups in need of palliative interventions (Sleeman et al., 2019). According to the WHO, around 70% of cancer-related deaths and 55% of cardiovascular deaths require palliative support (World Health Organization, 2020). The need for palliative care continues to rise due to increased life expectancy, late-stage disease diagnosis, and overburdened healthcare systems (Radbruch et al., 2020).

In Pakistan, nurses are frequently underprepared to deliver palliative care due to inadequate formal education and insufficient clinical exposure in this specialty (Shaikh & Haran, 2020). Most nursing programs offer limited content related to palliative care, resulting in a lack of confidence among nurses when dealing with dying patients or managing symptoms such as pain and breathlessness (Eke et al., 2017). Nurses' discomfort in discussing death or providing end-of-life care may stem from cultural norms, religious beliefs, and the taboo nature of death in many societies, including Pakistan (Budkaew & Chumworathayi, 2013). These challenges affect not only care quality but also the

psychological wellbeing of both the nurse and the patient (Kassa et al., 2014).

Self-efficacy plays a crucial role in influencing a nurse's ability to deliver high-quality palliative care. Nurses with higher self-efficacy tend to manage complex patient needs with greater confidence and resilience (Bandura, 1997). Studies show that self-efficacy contributes to better communication, symptom management, and emotional support in palliative settings (Reid et al., 2018). In contrast, low self-efficacy among nurses is associated with stress, task avoidance, and lower quality of care (Mulji & Sachwani, 2017). Many nurses report feeling emotionally unprepared to deal with patients at the end of life, and this lack of readiness negatively affects their performance (Ayed et al., 2015). Adequate training in symptom management, communication, and ethical decision-making is essential to build self-efficacy (Trueman & Parker, 2006).

Attitudes toward palliative care also shape how nurses respond to patient needs. Positive attitudes promote empathetic care and encourage nurses to provide holistic support encompassing physical, emotional, and spiritual aspects of patient wellbeing (Shad & Hafeez, 2011). Negative attitudes, including fear of death or discomfort with terminal illness, may lead to avoidance behaviors or inadequate symptom control (Budkaew & Chumworathayi, 2013). Nurses who receive formal palliative care training tend to develop more positive attitudes and are more willing to engage with dying patients (Reid et al., 2018). Educational interventions can help shift negative perceptions and empower nurses to face challenges with a more constructive mindset (Thomas et al., 2015).

The role of nurses in palliative care settings extends beyond clinical interventions to include communication with families, coordinating care with other professionals, and offering emotional support (Eke et al., 2017). In Pakistan, nurses are often the most accessible health professionals in hospitals and play a vital role in continuous patient monitoring and comfort care (Shaikh & Haran, 2020). However, they frequently work under resource constraints, with limited support from institutional policies or clinical guidelines on palliative care (Mpanga Sebuyira et al., 2003). These systemic gaps hinder the

development of competence and confidence required for effective care (Nishtar et al., 2021). Understanding and improving nurses' attitudes and self-efficacy is essential for enhancing the delivery of palliative care in such low-resource settings.

There is a critical need to investigate the psychological readiness of nurses in providing palliative care through assessing their attitudes and self-efficacy levels. Research suggests that improving both components through structured training and ongoing professional development may significantly enhance patient care outcomes (Kassa et al., 2014; Radbruch et al., 2020). A better understanding of these variables will help inform policy, curriculum development, and in-service training programs in Pakistan and similar contexts. Fostering a skilled and confident nursing workforce is key to ensuring the integration of palliative care as a standard component of quality healthcare services (Connor & Bermedo, 2020; Thomas et al., 2015).

Methodology

This study employed a correlational, cross-sectional quantitative research design to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and self-efficacy of nurses toward palliative care in Pakistan. A deductive approach was followed under the philosophical framework of positivism, focusing on measurable variables and objective analysis. The research was conducted among nurses working in various departments of the Children's Hospital, Lahore. A non-probability convenient sampling technique was used to select participants. The sample size was 171 nurses.

The structured questionnaire was divided into three sections:

- Section A: Demographic information (e.g., age, gender, education, family system, birth order)
- Section B: Independent variables (attitude and self-efficacy)
- Section C: Dependent variable (knowledge of palliative care)

Data Collection Procedure

Prior to data collection, approval was obtained from the Board of Studies (BOS) of Superior University, and official permission letters were issued to the

target hospital. Ethical clearance was secured to ensure the protection of participants' rights and well-being. After institutional permissions were granted, the researcher conducted a pilot study, followed by the main data collection phase.

Participants who met the inclusion criteria were approached in person, and the purpose of the study was clearly explained. Informed written consent was obtained from each participant prior to participation. The questionnaires were distributed directly to the participants, and they were requested to complete them in the presence of the researcher. Participants were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses, and they were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. Incomplete questionnaires were discarded and not included in the final analysis.

Data Analysis Procedure

The collected data were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 23. The analysis focused on both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize demographic characteristics and response distributions. For inferential analysis, Pearson correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between nurses' knowledge, attitudes, and self-efficacy toward palliative care. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$ for all statistical tests.

Results and analysis

The study included 171 female participants, with no male respondents. Most participants held a Generic BSN (35.1%), followed by Diploma in Nursing (29.2%), Post RN BSN (22.2%), and MSN (13.5%). The majority belonged to joint families (62%), while 38% lived in nuclear families. In terms of birth order, 42.1% were first-born, 30.4% middle-born, 20.5% last-born, and 7% were the only child [Table 1].

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 171)

Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	171	100.0
	Male	0	0.0
Education	Diploma in Nursing	50	29.2
	Generic BSN	60	35.1
	Post RN BSN	38	22.2
	MSN	23	13.5
Family System	Joint	106	62.0
	Nuclear	65	38.0
Birth Order	First Born	72	42.1
	Middle Born	52	30.4
	Last Born	35	20.5
	Only Child	12	7.0

Figure 1: Type of family of participants

Figure 1 shows that the majority of the respondents (62.0%, n=106) belonged to a joint family system, while 38.0% (n=65) were from nuclear families. This indicates a higher prevalence of joint family structures among the participants.

The descriptive statistics indicate that the Palliative Care scale had a mean of 31.19 (SD = 6.84), with a high internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = .992$), and a positively skewed distribution (Skewness = .992, Kurtosis = 1.995). The Self-efficacy scale had a mean of 18.03 (SD = 4.46), showing near-normal distribution (Skewness = .180, Kurtosis = -.215). For

the Attitude scale, the mean score was 54.69 (SD = 13.19), also reflecting normality with minimal skewness and kurtosis (Skewness = .049, Kurtosis = -.328). Overall, the scales demonstrated good internal reliability and acceptable distribution properties for further analysis [Table 2].

Table 2: Psychometric properties for Palliative Care, Self-efficacy and Attitude

Scales		Cronbach's		Skewness	Kurtosis
	Ranges	M	SD		
Palliative Care	20.0-60.0	31.19	6.84	.992	1.995
Self-efficacy	10.0-30.0	18.03	4.46	.180	-.215
Attitude	26.0-92.0	54.69	13.19	.049	-.328

The mean score for palliative care was 31.19 (SD = 6.84), which showed a significant positive correlation with self-efficacy ($r = .256, p < .001$) and attitude ($r = .344, p < .001$). Self-efficacy had a mean of 18.03 (SD = 4.46) and was significantly correlated with attitude

($r = .351, p < .001$). Attitude had the highest mean score of 54.69 (SD = 13.19), indicating a generally positive perception. All correlations were statistically significant at the $***p < .001$ level, reflecting strong associations among the variables [Table 3].

Table 3: Correlation Between Palliative Care, Self-Efficacy, and Attitude Among Nursing Students.

Variables	n	M	SD	1.	2.	3.
13. Palliative Care	171	31.19	6.84	-	.256***	.344***
2. Self-efficacy	171	18.03	4.46	-	-	.351***
3. Attitude	171	54.69	13.19	-	-	-

In Step I of the regression analysis, gender showed a significant positive effect ($\beta = .26^{**}$) on the attitude towards palliative care. Palliative care itself also had a

small but significant influence ($\beta = .06^{**}$). These results suggest that gender may be a stronger predictor of attitude in this context [Table 4].

Table 4: Linear Regression Analysis for the Prediction of Palliative Care

Variables	Palliative Care
Attitude	β
Step I	.06**
Gender	.26**

Discussion

The present study aimed to examine the relationship between nurses' knowledge, attitudes, and self-efficacy toward palliative care in a pediatric hospital setting in Pakistan. The results revealed that nurses demonstrated moderate levels of knowledge and self-efficacy, along with a generally positive attitude toward palliative care. These findings align with previous research emphasizing the importance of attitudinal and cognitive readiness among healthcare

providers for effective palliative care delivery (World Health Organization, 2020). The positive correlations among the three variables indicate that improving one area may positively influence the others, highlighting the need for integrated educational interventions (Kassa et al., 2014). The study revealed that most nurses had moderate knowledge about palliative care, which is consistent with findings from Trueman and Parker (2006), who reported similar trends in clinical nurses working in

general hospitals. Limited exposure to formal palliative care training, especially in low-resource settings like Pakistan, contributes to knowledge gaps (Shaikh & Haran, 2020). Unlike developed nations where structured palliative care training is integrated into nursing curricula, Pakistan still faces challenges in this regard (Ayed et al., 2015). This gap stresses the urgent need for capacity-building initiatives targeting nursing professionals who frequently engage with end-of-life care patients.

In terms of attitude, the findings showed that nurses generally held a positive outlook toward palliative care, which supports the conclusions drawn by Eke et al. (2017), who found that nurses' empathy and compassion influence patient-centered care practices. However, these results differ from Budkaew and Chumworathayi (2013), who found negative attitudes among nurses due to emotional exhaustion and fear of death. Cultural values, religious beliefs, and workplace environment could account for this contrast. In Pakistan, nurses' spiritual beliefs may foster a more compassionate attitude toward end-of-life care, even when clinical resources are lacking (Mpanga Sebuyira et al., 2003).

Self-efficacy emerged as a significant predictor of both knowledge and attitude in this study, consistent with Bandura's (1997) theory that individuals with higher self-efficacy are more likely to engage confidently in complex tasks, such as providing palliative care. Similar findings were observed by Reid et al. (2018), who demonstrated that nurses with strong self-efficacy were more capable of handling ethical dilemmas and pain management in terminally ill patients. These results suggest that interventions aimed at enhancing self-efficacy could have a cascading positive effect on both knowledge and attitude.

Interestingly, gender was found to be a significant predictor of attitude toward palliative care, with female nurses expressing more favorable views. This aligns with previous studies indicating that women often display higher emotional intelligence and empathetic tendencies, which are crucial in palliative settings (Mulji & Sachwani, 2017). However, in contrast to Western studies, where male nurses also demonstrated high attitudinal scores when adequately trained, this difference in Pakistan may

reflect deeper cultural roles and expectations placed on female caregivers (Connor & Bermedo, 2020). Comparing these findings with the WHO's (2017) global mapping study reveals a persistent disparity between high-income and low-income countries regarding palliative care accessibility and training. While the global north has seen significant progress in mainstreaming palliative care, developing countries still face institutional and educational barriers (World Health Organization, 2020). As emphasized by Nishtar et al. (2021), the integration of palliative care into primary healthcare systems and nursing education in Pakistan remains fragmented, requiring systemic policy reforms.

Conclusion

This study explored the relationship between nurses' knowledge, attitudes, and self-efficacy toward palliative care in a pediatric hospital setting in Pakistan. The findings revealed a moderate level of knowledge and self-efficacy among nurses, coupled with generally positive attitudes toward palliative care. A significant positive correlation was identified among all three variables, indicating that enhanced knowledge and self-efficacy are associated with more favorable attitudes. Gender also emerged as a significant predictor of attitude, highlighting the influence of sociocultural factors in shaping perceptions toward end-of-life care. The study underscores the crucial role of well-informed, confident, and emotionally resilient nursing staff in delivering effective palliative care. Addressing the gaps in knowledge and skill through structured education and support systems can help improve the overall quality of palliative services, particularly in low-resource settings like Pakistan.

Recommendations

1. Integrate Palliative Care into Nursing Curriculum

Nursing institutions should incorporate comprehensive palliative care modules into undergraduate and postgraduate programs to strengthen foundational knowledge and clinical competency.

2. Organize Regular In-Service Training

Healthcare institutions must offer ongoing training

workshops focused on symptom management, communication skills, cultural sensitivity, and ethical decision-making in palliative care.

3. Enhance Nurses' Self-Efficacy Through Mentorship

Establish structured mentorship programs and peer-support systems to build nurses' confidence and self-efficacy in handling complex palliative care cases.

4. Promote Gender-Sensitive Training Approaches

Recognize and address gender-specific perspectives in training programs to ensure equitable development of positive attitudes toward palliative care across all staff.

5. Raise Public and Institutional Awareness

Launch awareness campaigns and policy dialogues that highlight the importance of palliative care as a basic human right, aligning with global health priorities.

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